

Supporting Information

Densely carboxylated graphene for synthesis of high-performing NASICON cathodes for Na-ion batteries

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Note S1. Determination of lateral crystallite size from Raman spectra

The lateral crystallite size (L_a) of the carbon samples was estimated from Raman spectroscopy based on the Tuinstra and Koenig equation (S1):¹

$$L_a(nm) = \frac{4.4}{\frac{I_D}{I_G}} \cdot \left(\frac{2.41}{E_L}\right)^4 \quad (S1)$$

where $I(D)$ and $I(G)$ represent the intensities of the D and G bands, respectively, and E_L is a laser energy, which is equal to 2.3308 eV for 532 nm. Given that the Raman spectra were deconvoluted according to Sadezky et al.,² we calculated L_a using the intensity of D1 and G bands.

Note S2. Kinetic analysis of cyclic voltammetry data

To assess the kinetics of NVP cathodes, power-law analysis was employed to elucidate the electrochemical processes during charge and discharge.³ The b -value, derived from the relationship $i_p = av^b$, was obtained from the slope of the $\log(i)$ versus $\log(v)$ plot at various potentials. A b -value of 0.5 indicates a diffusion-controlled process, while 1.0 corresponds to a surface-controlled mechanism. Intermediate values observed across most potentials suggest a combination of both.

Note S3. Calculation of Na⁺ diffusion coefficient in GITT experiment

The galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) was carried out in a PAT-Cell (El-Cell) using an NVP@GA cathode and a sodium metal counter electrode. Prior to the measurement, the cathode was conditioned by two charge-discharge cycles at 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, and 1 A g_{EM}⁻¹. The GITT protocol consisted of a sequence of 15 min current pulses at 11.7 mA g_{EM}⁻¹, each followed by a 30-min relaxation at open-circuit potential. The apparent Na⁺ diffusion coefficient (D_{Na^+}) was determined from the simplified Weppner-Huggins equation, valid for small current perturbations (S2):^{4,5}

$$D_{Na^+} = \frac{4}{\pi\tau} \left(\frac{n_M V_M}{M_r S}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta E_s}{\Delta E_t}\right)^2 \quad (S2)$$

where τ is the pulse duration (s); n_m and V_m are the molar quantity (mol) and molar volume (cm³ mol⁻¹) of the active material; M_r is the molar mass (g mol⁻¹); S is the electrode surface area (cm²); ΔE_t is the potential change during the current pulse (corrected for iR drop); and ΔE_s is the steady-state potential change after relaxation.

Note S4. Kinetic analysis of charge-transfer processes at the carbon-NVP interface

Exchange current density I_0 at SEI/electrolyte interface at different states of charge was calculated based on the following equation (S3):

$$I_0 = \frac{RT}{nFAR_{CT1}} \quad (S3)$$

where R stands for gas constant ($R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), T – absolute temperature (298.15 K in our case), n – number of transferred electrons, that is one for Na^+ , F – Faraday constant ($F = 96485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$), A – geometric surface area of the cathode, R_{CT1} – charge transfer resistance obtained from EIS. High exchange current density represents fast Na^+ exchange through the CEI layer, which is a desirable property, especially at high charge/discharge rates.⁶

Na^+ solid-state diffusion coefficient of Na^+ through SEI (D_{SEI}) at different states of charge was calculated based on the Warburg coefficient ($\sigma = Y_0^{-1}$) (S4):

$$D_{SEI} = \frac{R^2 T^2}{2A^2 n^4 F^4 C^2 \sigma^2} \quad (S4)$$

where C – stands for concentration of Na^+ in the electrolyte (1 mol dm^{-3} in this work).

Figure S1. SEM and TEM micrographs of (a,b) GA and (c,d) NG.

Figure S2. XRD diffractograms for (a) NVP@AA, (b) NVP@NG, and (c) comparison of materials with a reference diffractogram.

Figure S3. High-resolution TEM images of (a) NVP@GA and (b) NVP@NG with magnified regions at the NVP/carbon interface. Fast Fourier transform (FFT) analyses acquired from the interfacial domains reveal well-defined diffraction spots on the NVP side, indicative of its crystalline order, whereas the carbon regions exhibit no discernible periodicity, consistent with their low-order character.

Figure S4. XPS survey spectra for NVP@AA, NVP@NG, and NVP@GA.

Figure S5. Deconvolution of C 1s high-resolution XPS spectra of NVP samples.

Figure S6. Initial cyclic voltammograms of (a) NVP@NG at 0.2 mV s^{-1} in the 2.0-4.2 V range vs Na/Na^+ and (b) NVP@AA at 0.1 mV s^{-1} in the 2.0-4.4 V range vs Na/Na^+ .

Figure S7. Fifth-cycle galvanostatic charge-discharge profiles of (a) NVP@NG and (b) NVP@AA cathodes, corresponding to the rate performance shown in Fig. 5b.

Figure S8. Cyclic voltammetry curves of the NVP@NG cathode at different scan rates.

Figure S9. Galvanostatic intermittent titration technique profiles: individual current pulses and relaxation during (a) charge and (b) discharge of NVP@GA.

Figure S10. (a) Charge profile of NVP@GA with indicated state of charge where EIS spectra were recorded. Equivalent circuit model used to fit the electrochemical impedance spectra of NVP@GA at the (b) fully sodiated (0% SoC) and desodiated (100% SoC) and (c) at the intermediate states of charge. R_b represents the bulk resistance (electrodes, electrolyte, separator and contacts), the high-frequency semicircle (R_{CT1} , Q_{CT1}) corresponds to the SEI/CEI layer; the mid-frequency arc (R_{CT2} , Q_{CT2}) represents interfacial charge transfer of Na⁺ ions; and the low-frequency Warburg element (Y_0) accounts for Na⁺ diffusion within the electrode.

Figure S11. Kinetic analysis of charge transfer across the carbon interface of NVP@GA as a function of state of charge. Shown are: (a) the charge-transfer resistance R_{CT1} , (b) the Na^+ diffusion coefficient obtained from GITT; (c) the exchange current density; and (d) the Na^+ diffusion coefficient extracted from the high-frequency EIS equivalent circuit; (e) the CPE magnitude parameter Q_1 ; (f) the CPE exponent n_1 .

Table S1. Elemental CHN analysis of the NVP samples.

Sample	C	H	N
NVP@GA	12.7	0.6	0.8
NVP@NG*	6.7	0.7	0.5
NVP@AA	10.3	1.0	1.1

* 2 mmol of AA was added to the synthetic mixture of NVP@NG to adjust the pH.

Table S2. Cell parameters for the NVP@GA, NVP@NG, and NVP@AA samples derived from Rietveld refinement.

Sample name	$a / \text{Å}$	$c / \text{Å}$
NVP@GA	8.72929(23)	21.80726(92)
NVP@NG	8.72854(25)	21.81830(99)
NVP@AA	8.73589(14)	21.83198(52)

Table S3. Deconvolution results of Raman spectra for NVP samples presented in Fig 4. I_D/I_G – intensity ratio and A_D/A_G – area ratio of respective bands.

Sample	Peak	Center Max	Area FitTP	Max Height	FWHM	Peak ratio	A_D/A_G	I_D/I_G
NVP@GA	D4	1201	10.29	0.154	198.2	D4/G	0.486	0.197
	D1	1347.3	54.54	0.900	175.2	D1/G	2.577	1.148
	D3	1512	14.02	0.324	167.7	D3/G	0.663	0.413
	G	1599.4	21.16	0.784	74.1	–	–	–
NVP@NG	D4	1202	9.07	0.107	202.9	D4/G	0.416	0.143
	D1	1348.4	56.36	0.899	143.4	D1/G	2.584	1.197
	D3	1514	12.76	0.246	161.6	D3/G	0.585	0.328
	G	1599.1	21.81	0.751	63.8	–	–	–
NVP@AA	D4	1203	8.87	0.161	152.2	D4/G	0.510	0.252
	D1	1342.5	51.53	0.839	169.4	D1/G	2.960	1.318
	D3	1513	22.19	0.426	193.0	D3/G	1.274	0.669
	G	1596.6	17.41	0.637	71.7	–	–	–

Table S4. Comparison of electrochemical properties of NVP cathodes for Na-ion storage. Current and capacity values refer to the mass of electrode material.

%	Active material	Carbon source	EM composition	Inorg. in EM (%) [*]	Cell	Q _{EM} (mAh g _{EM} ⁻¹) @ rate (A g _{EM} ⁻¹) [*]	Ref.
1	NVP@GA 14.1% of CHN by elemental analysis	Graphene acid	NVP@GA:CB:PVDF 85:8:7	73	1M NaPF ₆ , EC:DEC (3:7), 5% FEC	90.0 @ 0.05 55.9 @ 15	This work
2	NVP@C-800, 6.6% of carbon by TGA	Citric acid	NVP@C800: CB: PVDF 80:10:10	74.7	1M NaClO ₄ in EC:DEC (1:1), 5% FEC	82.4 @ 0.019 52 @ 2.81	⁷ Zhou et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2021
3	NVP/C-10	Citric acid Carbon nanotubes	NVP/C-10:CB:PVDF 80:10:10	73.6	1 M NaClO ₄ in EC/DMC (1:1), 5% FEC	82.6 @ 0.0184 60.9 @ 5.62	⁸ Chen et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2018
4	ME-NASICON	Citric acid Ascorbic acid	ME-NASICON:CB:PVDF 70:20:10	≤70	1 M NaClO ₄ in PC, 5% FEC	113 @ 0.0084 52.8 @ 1.68	⁹ Zhu et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2025
5	KAS_4-NVP	Citric acid	KAS_4-NVP:CB:PVDF 75:20:5	≤75	1 M NaClO ₄ in EC/DEC (1:1), 5% FEC	86.5 @ 0.044 59.3 @ 4.39	¹⁰ Chen et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2025
6	FNV-2	trisodium citrate dihydrate MWCNTs (0.5wt%)	FNV-2:CB:PVDF 85:5:10	≤85	1 M NaClO ₄ in EC/DEC (1:1), 5% FEC	95.1 @ 0.01 82.8 @ 1	⁸ Kadam et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2023
7	NMTP WC	Citric acid, Acetates, super P, tetraisopropoxide	NMTP WC:CB:PVDF 80:10:10	≤80	1 M NaPF ₆ in diglyme	96 @ 0.028 58.4 @ 0.28	¹¹ Xia et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2025
8	NVP/N-C2	Citric acid Glucose, urea	NVP/N-C2:CB:PVDF 70:20:10	67.6	NaPF ₆ in EC:DMC	81.2 @ 0.0082 77.7 @ 0.082 69.6 @ 0.82 64.54 @ 1.64	¹² Li et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2025
9	NVP@C-MWCNTs, 2.83% of carbon by TGA	Oxalic acid, MWCNTs	NVP@C@MWCNTs: CB: PVDF 80:10:10	77.7	1M NaPF ₆ in diglyme	84.8 @ 0.08 80.3 @ 1.6	¹³ Wang et al., <i>Chem. Eng. J.</i> 2018
10	NVP@C-CC, free-standing EM, 8% of carbon in NVP@C by TGA	Citric acid, carbon cloth	NVP@C:carbon cloth 20:80	18.4	1M NaClO ₄ EC:DEC (1:1), 5% FEC	23.3 @ 0.023 14 @ 4.68	¹⁴ Guo et al., <i>Nano Energy</i> 2018

11	NVP@C nanoflake spheres; 9.72% of carbon	Sodium oleate	NVP@C:CB: PVDF 75:15:10	67.7	1M NaClO ₄ PC:FEC (95:5)	77.6 @ 0.047 48 @ 9.41	¹⁵ Cao et al., <i>Nano Energy</i> 2019
12	NVP@C 3D, nanoflakes; 10.53% carbon	Span 80, paraffin	NVP@C:CB:PVDF 75:15:10	67.1	1M NaClO ₄ in PC:FEC (95:5)	85.7 @ 0.044 65.8 @ 8.82	¹⁶ Zhao et al., <i>Chem. Eng. J.</i> 2018
13	NVP-C, 7% of carbon by TGA	Sugar	NVP@C:CB:PVDF 70:18:12	64.4	1M NaPF ₆ in diglyme	72.8 @ 0.0036 60.9 @ 0.36	¹⁷ Pandit et al., <i>Nano Energy</i> 2022
14	NVPF/NVP@C Carbon content in AM is n.a.	Citric acid	NVPF/NVP @C:CB:PVDF 70:20:10	≤70	1M NaPF ₆ in diglyme	80.3 @ 0.045 61.6 @ 0.9	¹⁸ Park et al., <i>J Mater. Chem. A</i> 2020
15	NVNiP-F2@C 6.27% of carbon by EDS	Citric acid	NVNiP-F2@C:CB:PVDF 80:10:10	75	1M NaPF ₆ in EC:PC (1:1)	93.6 @ 0.01 84 @ 0.51	¹⁹ Essehli et al., <i>Adv. Sci.</i> 2023
16	NVMNP@C, 2.34% of C by TGA	Citric acid	NVMNP@C: CNTs:PVDF 70:20:10	68.4	1M NaClO ₄ in PC:EC with 5% FEC	54.6 @ 0.05 46.9 @ 3	²⁰ Xu et al., <i>Small Struct.</i> 2024
17	NVFP-650@C 6.5% of C by TGA	Oxalic acid	NVFP:CB:PVDF 70:20:10	67.2	1M NaClO ₄ solvent n.a.	72 @ 0.007 47.5 @ 1.4	²¹ Zhu et al., <i>Small Methods</i> 2025
18	Na ₃ V ₂ O ₂ (PO ₄) ₂ F, C content n.a.	Oxalic acid	AM:CB:PVDF 60:30:10	≤60	1 M NaClO ₄ in PC, 5% FEC	81.4 @ 0.0078 68.4 @ 0.78	²² Zheng et al., <i>Appl Mater Today</i> 2021
19	NVPOF, no carbon shell	Oxalic acid	NVPOF-80:CB:CMC 70:20:10	70	1M NaClO ₄ in EC:PC (1:1), 5% FEC	87.2 @ 0.091 48 @ 9.1	²³ Yu et al., <i>Sci Bull</i> 2025
20	2% PANI@NVPF, 2.63% of carbon by TGA	Citric acid, PANI	2% PANI@NVPF:CB:PVDF 70:20:10	68.2	1M NaClO ₄ in PC:FEC (95:5%)	78.8 @ 0.045 59.5 @ 0.45	²⁴ Missaoui et al., <i>ACS AMI</i> 2024
21	NVAMP-0.3 3.43% of carbon by TGA	Oxalic acid, citric acid	AM:CB:PVDF 7:2:1	67.6	1 M NaClO ₄ EC:PC (1:1) 5%FEC	65.8 @ 0.07 61.4 @ 2.8	²⁵ Liu et al., <i>Chem Eng J</i> 2024
22	NV ₂ O/NV ₃ P@C@SWCNTs, ~6% SWCNTs (in reaction mixture)	Citric acid, SWCNTs	NV ₂ O/NV ₃ P@C@SWCNTs:CB:PVDF 8:1:1	~75.2	1M NaClO ₄ EC:PC (1:1), 5% FEC	84.2 @ 0.047 55.2 @ 9.4	²⁶ Wang et al., <i>J. Mater. Sci. Technol.</i> 2021
23	NVPFO/MCLC@C 4.6 % of carbon by TGA	Melamine, cyanuric acid and citric acid, alkali lignin	NVPFO/MCLC@C CB:PVDF 8:1:1	76.3	1M NaClO ₄ in EC:PC (1:1), 5%FEC	93.8 @ 0.1 42.24 @ 10.0	²⁷ Ma et al., <i>Chem Eng J</i> 2024
24	NVOPF, zero carbon content	Citric acid	NVOPF:CB:PTFE 7:2:1	70.0	1M NaClO ₄ in PC, 2 %FEC	87.4 @ 0.0091 69.9 @ 1.82	²⁸ Li et al., <i>Adv Mater</i> 2024
25	NVP@C, 20.67% of carbon based on TGA	Citric acid	NVP@C:CB:PVDF 8:1:1	63.7	1M NaClO ₄ in EC:DEC (1:1)	79.2 @ 0.047 54.6 @ 0.936	²⁹ Kate et al., <i>J Energy Storage</i> 2023

*EM-specific parameters and NVP content were derived from the publications' data:

$$\text{NVP in EM (\%)} = \omega_{\text{NVP@C in EM (\%)}} \times (100 - \omega_{\text{C in NVP@C (\%)})}$$

where $\omega_{C \text{ in NVP@C}}$ is the reported content of carbon in NVP@C active material or change of mass in TGA in the 100°C to 630°C temperature range;

$$Q_{EM}(\text{mAh g}_{EM}^{-1}) = Q_{AM}(\text{mAh g}_{AM}^{-1}) \times \omega_{AM}$$

where ω_{AM} is mass fraction of NVP@C active material in electrode material;

$$I_{EM}(\text{A g}_{EM}^{-1}) = I_{AM}(\text{A g}_{AM}^{-1}) \times \omega_{AM};$$

For C-rate to specific current recalculation theoretical capacity was used assuming NVP@carbon shell as the AM.

Table S5. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy fitting parameters for NVP@GA cathode.

SO C (%)	R_b ($\Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	R_{CT1} ($\Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	Q_1 (S s^n)	n_1	R_{CT2} ($\Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	Q_2 (S s^n)	n_2	W ($\text{S s}^{0.5}$)	Std. Error (%)
0	1.49	13.5	3.09×10^{-4}	0.709	-	4.0×10^{-2}	1	0.029	2.8
11	1.58	4.6	3.69×10^{-4}	0.709	0.7	1.1×10^{-2}	1	0.347	1.5
22	1.59	3.8	3.16×10^{-4}	0.727	0.8	1.3×10^{-2}	1	0.495	1.3
33	1.60	3.3	3.02×10^{-4}	0.736	0.8	1.3×10^{-2}	1	0.551	1.3
44	1.61	2.9	3.02×10^{-4}	0.741	0.9	1.3×10^{-2}	1	0.586	1.3
56	1.61	2.6	3.26×10^{-4}	0.737	0.9	1.5×10^{-2}	1	0.625	1.3
67	1.61	2.3	3.02×10^{-4}	0.731	1.0	1.5×10^{-2}	1	0.596	1.2
78	1.61	2.1	3.97×10^{-4}	0.728	1.1	1.6×10^{-2}	1	0.443	1.4
89	1.61	1.9	4.39×10^{-4}	0.725	1.0	1.5×10^{-2}	1	0.192	1.2
100	1.61	1.6	4.55×10^{-4}	0.732	-	7.5×10^{-2}	0.976	0.183	1.9

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